

A PROPOSAL FOR IMPLEMENTING A NOTIFICATION SYSTEM FOR OBSOLETE FILE FORMATS AND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract – This paper builds upon the previous paper “Monitoring File Format Obsolescence in repositories”. This first phase was focused on evaluating a method to analyze the life cycle of file formats and identify their developmental stages. The term “life cycle” refers to the popularity of a file format over time, illustrated through a graph that depicts its rise and/or decline throughout the years. This information is crucial for both Preservation Watch and Preservation Planning.

The method of the first phase also explored the possibility of predicting a file format's life cycle. This was achieved by utilizing the observed life cycle. The dataset was divided into a training set and a test set, with the training set being compared to the observed life cycle

In this paper the method from the first phase will be extended with extra capabilities and a solution for monitoring the life cycle. The monitoring will include notifications when action needs to be taken. Additionally, we will investigate the relationship between the file format life cycle and the application life cycle.

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how to perform these activities is a challenge for many institutions. Certainly if it needs to be executed at scale and finding time in the busy schedule to work on these activities is difficult. The Dutch Digital Heritage Network (DDHN) wants to support heritage institutes in the Netherlands to perform Preservation Watch. For that reason an expert group on Preservation Watch was formed. One of the projects of the Preservation Watch working group resulted in the work previously presented at iPres in the paper “Monitoring File Format Obsolescence in repositories. An applied method”[1]. In that paper a method is described based on the Bass Diffusion Model. The method was used to analyse repository data from participating organisations and found some expected file formats life cycle. The Microsoft Office formats showed a clear life cycle in older binary file formats and the newer OpenXML based file formats, for example between XLS and XLSX. [2] With one exception, Microsoft Access. The older MDB file format was more popular than the newer ACCDB. [3] This could be explained from the local context of the organisation. This observation makes clear that the method can't be used to fully automate the method and expert knowledge is necessary to interpret the results with knowledge of the local context.

I. INTRODUCTION

Preservation Planning and Preservation Watch are challenging activities for organisations. Knowing

II. CHALLENGES DURING THE FIRST PHASE

In the first phase [4] the method also tried to predict the life cycle of the file format, by splitting the data in a training set and a test set. The prediction of the life cycle didn't give reliable results. The Bass Diffusion model is not expressive enough to cope with all the sudden changes in the data, like a sudden increase after a long decrease, for example. This can happen in predicting the life cycle. Also with the erratic data when the data drops to zero.

Another challenge encountered was the interpretation of the plots. During workshops, it was clear that it is not easy to fully understand what the meaning is of a plot and what action to take. Although looking for the first time for some participants at their data was already an important step, but the interpretation was not easy or obvious.

What was apparent in the results of the first phase of the study was that context of the results are very important to understand the outcomes. This means that fully-automation is probably not possible, although with some new functionality the process can be semi-automated. To try to add some context we used global datasets like the Common crawl dataset [5] to validate if these kind of datasets can be used as a validation of the dataset of a repository. This means if an unexpected peak in a repository is also visible in the global dataset. This could mean that the peak is not a local trend, but a global trend.

During the first phase, it turned out that the Common Crawl data set, can't be a substitute for a global data set. One reason for this is that Common Crawl primarily contains web archive data and repositories contain file formats that are not web archives. For example HTML is important in a Web archive, while in an institutional repository it is likely less relevant. Another reason is that the Common Crawl data is recent, it starts in 2014, but the aggregated results start in 2017. Which is recent compared to some of the file formats still in use dating back as far as 1987.

Another limitation from the first phase method, is that it can only analyse one file format at the time, while there are interesting relations to see between certain file formats. Experts already know this, but it is important to see that this relationship is also visible in the plots. Like already mentioned, the relation was apparent between the Microsoft Office

file formats of DOC and DOCX, XLS and XLSX and PPT and PPTX, with the exception of Microsoft Access file formats (MDB and ACCDB). This exception can be explained by the local context: the files come from a collection of archaeological datasets. The files are created using a specific methodology in the Netherlands for archaeological excavations. This methodology uses MDB files to store information and during the pandemic archeologists couldn't excavate and so they created reports. This meant a big influx of MDB files. [3]

One of the biggest limitations of the first phase method is that there is no relation between file formats and applications. While it is clear for experts that there is a connection between file formats and application, it was not clear how that connection could be formalised in a method that could be (semi-)automated. Different sources were evaluated for the necessary information. [6] The conclusion was that the data model of Wikidata was the most suitable option. It also has lots of data to start with it.

III. IMPROVEMENTS TO THE METHOD

In order to improve the method, the method needs to handle erratic data better. To help understanding the plot better, it is necessary to show more information on the plot. Important information is for example the reliability of the plot. It is also important to raise awareness that the fit on the plot is less important, but that locating the peak is more important. Because once the peak is found, other information can be derived, like reliability with bootstrap resampling [7] or standard deviation. [8]

The reliability can be determined by using the narrowness of a peak. With a broad peak for example the plot is less reliable and that could mean the file format is probably not obsolete. It is not the only argument to come to that conclusion, also for example the number of data points needed for a reliable plot is important information to show. For determining how many data points are needed for a reliable plot, the bootstrap resampling [7] can be used. It is a technique that takes a new sample in the current plot, but with slightly different random selected subset. This needs to be reiterated for 63,5% [9] of the total number of data points. This is called bootstrap runs. The result of the runs will tell how many data points are needed to have a reliable plot.

Another conclusion after the first phase of the research was that prediction is not reliable enough to be useful. This conclusion showed that a change in strategy was necessary. Instead of predicting, monitoring the progress of a file format over time is a better strategy. It probably also aligns better with Preservation Watch as a strategy. By regularly monitoring the life cycle the changes can be followed and the necessary action can be taken. The changes are gradually, so regular can mean yearly or every few years. The process could also be automated and a notification when a change occurs, could be send.

To implement monitoring there are three important points on a plot available, the inflection points and the peak. These points are visible in fig 1 as vertical lines on the plot.

Fig. 1 Plot with peak and inflection points (2024) CC-BY-SA-4.0, Ralph C.A. Rippe

The first inflection point on the left hand side is the first inflection point. It is a sign that the peak is coming. It is less important, but there are scenarios where it can be used to predict when a peak is coming. In this scenario the plot is not a complete curve, but only a raising plot is visible. But as prediction is not the goal, this is less important at the moment. The progress will become apparent when the monitoring continues anyway, the progress of the first inflection point and prediction of the peak is also an event that could be followed during monitoring.

The second point is the peak, this is when the file format reaches its top. This is an important point as it can be used in many calculations and locating the peak is important step to take. The third point is the second inflection point. This is a sign that the file format is in decline. It is an important notification to monitor the file format closer and maybe prepare to

take action. It doesn't mean there is an immediate problem, but a Preservation Plan needs to be created to monitor the potential preservation risk. [10]

The Bass Diffusion model was and is a useful model to start with. It doesn't need much input and it is capable of handling some erratic data. This is certainly useful as it is difficult to get the necessary data from repositories. This is an observation from workshops. It was difficult for organizations to export the relevant data for various reasons although only file creation date and file format information (extension, mime type or PUID) was needed.

An alternative method for Bass Model can be Spline Regression [11] as it has some comparable features as Bass Model, but it can better handle the erratic data. For example compared to the Bass Model, Spline Regression handles zero values better in the available data. Spline Regression is similar enough that the improvements discussed can be used in this model as well. It is just one possible alternative model, but it finds the middle ground between a simple method and not needing too much information to work. Other more complex methods need more data and don't necessary produce better results because of the erratic data. This will be further tested in the future.

To add more context to the results of a plot, as previously discussed a global dataset isn't useable, but there can be an alternative where the data from different repositories can be combined as a substitute for the global dataset. This is possible because the data doesn't contain privacy sensitive information. The important step that needs to be taken is getting enough data to create this combined dataset. Providers of preservation systems are uniquely positioned to have this data available and, after consent from their costumers, create this type of dataset to compare the individual repository results with. The comparison needs to be independent of the absolute numbers so that big repositories don't influence the outcomes and the comparison should only uses significant differences. For these comparisons, methods like ANOVA [12] are available. The method can be used to compare different "groups". For the amount of overlap between the different "groups" the Spearman correlation [13] can be used.

The "groups" can be repositories, the individual repository compared to the global aggregate data set

or to individual repositories. But any comparison is possible. Examples of possible “groups” are MIME types, PRONOM IDs, file extensions, or file format categories like image formats. All kinds of comparisons are possible, but this doesn’t mean that every comparison is useful. That’s why it is necessary to have an expert to determine the usefulness of a comparison. Comparing image file formats, or even the broader category of image formats against for example TIFF, can be useful. However, comparing TIFF with a word processing format like DOCX is probably not useful. The expert can be helped by assessing the reliability of the comparison. For example, the Levene test [14] can be used to provide that extra information on the significance of the comparison. It gives more insight if the significance is coincidental or not.

Another comparison that is useful in the field of Digital Preservation is the comparison between a file format and its successor. As previously mentioned the case of the Microsoft Office files, where for example XLSX is the successor of XLS. This means that the plot of XLS needs to decline as XLSX starts to rise. The relevant parts of the plot need to be compared. In the file format that is declining, the relevant part is the declining part and in the successor the increasing part is relevant. More specific the time between the two peaks and the overlapping parts in the two plots. On fig 2 this is the horizontal line between the two peaks.

Fig. 2: Crossing of the tails of two plots (2024) CC-BY-SA-4.0, Ralph C.A. Rippe

This technique is called time-lagged cross correlation or lagged regression [15]. The correlation between the two plots can be determined with Spearman correlation [13], it tells how much time the two plots overlap. The height of the Spearman correlation is depended on the use case and the field where it is applied. Because this is the first time this

technique is proposed in this use case, there is no indication how long the overlap needs to be before action needs to be taken. It depends on how precise measurements are. In this case the data is coarse and not precise, so it is expected that the overlap will be on the lower side. In fields like Physics with very precise measurements the gap can be smaller, for example an overlap of 95% is on the low side in that field. While other fields like Psychology, the gap can be wider and an overlap of 50% is considered high. It is expected that in the field of Digital Preservation the gap will be wide and the overlap will be low, because of the lack of precision of the data. But only time will tell.

As previously mentioned, Wikidata is a good resource for the connection between applications and file formats. This means the data model and properties of Wikidata can be used to create a life cycle for applications as well. This life cycle can be used to compare with the file format life cycle. The hypothesis is if applications are getting obsolete, the support for a file format is declining and the file format is in danger. The proposed methodology uses the same technique as with file formats. This means that everything written in this paper regarding file formats also applies to application. For example a monitoring system could be implemented using the inflection points as a notification signal on when to take action. The combination of file format and application notification signals helps to get warnings in advance, so it is still possible to prepare and make a Preservation Plan with a Preservation Action. Your preservation policy define what that action needs to be. That can for example be a file migration or use emulation. A Preservation Risk can be created and monitored. [10]

There will be two methods proposed to create a life cycle for applications. The first method is simpler and doesn’t need as much information as the second method. The first method is simpler, because the link between file format and application is indirect. This means that an expert needs to reach the conclusion of obsolescence based on interpretation of the data and the plots of file format and application are two separate plots.

Both methods are based on the same technique of calculating an activity score. This is used in the medical field to calculate “time to event” analysis or survival analysis [16]. In the context of Digital Preservation the activity score is used to create an

overview of the different version of an application. The major version of an application get a higher weight than the minor versions. Every version has a release date. For every version the time between releases multiplied with the weight creates a score per version. The score can also be added up to a score for multiple applications. This score is used as a value in the plot. The plot is the combination of score for a version and the release period. With release period is a grouping of the release dates in for example months or quarters. This will create a similar plot for one or more applications as was created for file formats. In case of multiple applications a plot with combined scores and release dates from the different versions of the applications is created. The output looks the same as earlier plots.

In Wikidata the scores can be created with information from “software version identifier” property. [17]

software version identifier	version	publication date	reference
	3.0	21 July 2011	▶ 1 reference
	3.19	8 February 2015	▶ 1 reference
	3.19.3	26 March 2015	▶ 1 reference

Fig. 3: Software Identifier Version on Wikidata from the Linux Kernel

As example, Fig. 3 shows different releases from the Linux Kernel operating system. The first release shown is release 3.0 which is a Major version and would get the highest weight, for example 3. The second release in Fig 3 is 3.19, this is a Minor version and gets a lower weight of 2 for example. The third release is the Patch version and could get the lowest weight of for example 1. Every release has a release date. In Fig. 3 it is called Publication Date. The difference between the previous publication date is calculated. The difference between version 3.19 and 3.19.3 is 46 days. This difference is multiplied for the weight. The score for 3.19.3 is 46 (1*46). The activity score can be extended further with more information. In Wikidata you also have a property called inception [18] and discontinued date [19]. They are used when an application was created and

when the development of an application stopped respectfully.

The results of the activity scores and release dates can be plotted and a Bass Model can be created. The advantage of this approach is that all the previous mentioned techniques about file formats can be used for applications as well, for example locating the peak and bootstrap resampling. [7] This also means the inflection points can be used as a notification system. The difference with the techniques mentioned for file format is that in this first technique more human interaction and knowledge is needed. For example an expert needs to know which applications can open which file format, because this is not included in this technique and is necessary to interpret the plots of a file format and the application for that file format.

The need for expert knowledge is also necessary because it is expected that the maturity of an application also plays a part in the activity score. When an application is more mature, it gets fewer updates as fewer bugs exist and features are more mature. This is expected to have influence on the activity score and the plot.

This influence needs to be studied more, but a possible research approach is, to evaluate the plots of file format and application. The application plot can show a decline because of maturity or deprecation. The peak of a mature application is expected to be different than the peak of the associated file format. While the peak of a deprecated application is expected to have a similar peak as the associated file format. Similar is meant in a mathematical sense and can be evaluated with the same techniques as mentioned earlier, for example ANOVA [12] and Spearman correlation. [13]

The second technique to determine the application life cycle uses the same method, but uses more information about file formats. It uses the information about which application or applications can read or write a file format. The difference between opening and saving is important, because the hypothesis in this case is that an application can open an older file format for longer time than it can save them. Software vendors try to encourage users to switch to a new application and file format [20].

The input for this method uses the properties “readable file format” [21] and “writable file format” [22] in Wikidata. These properties are used to

describe which application can respectfully open or save a specific file format. This second technique creates a separate application activity score for application that can open and save a file format. This will create two overlapping plots similar to the time-lagged cross correlation / lagged regression [15] explained earlier. As explained the relevant part is between the peak of an application that can open a certain file format and the peak of an application that can save a certain file format. The similarity or overlap between the two plots can be calculated with Spearman correlation [13]. When the difference between the two peaks becomes too big, an action needs to be taken. In this case as well, what too big means is something that will become clear with more experience. It is difficult to predict and depends on the precision of the data, as mentioned earlier. In this use case, a higher overlap is expected since the processes of opening and saving a file format by an application occur closer together in time. This is because new application versions are released more frequent and the software vendors to provide limited support for older applications. This means it is expected that the plots will be closer together. However, this still needs to be proven in practice, as there may be other factors that could influence the results. It is guessing at this stage.

As in the first technique, the maturity and deprecation of an application need to be distinguished. To interpret the plots you need the application open and save plots created with the second technique and compare it with the application plots from the first technique, without the extra link between file format information. If the plots overlap closely then the decline in activity is probably a sign of maturity and not of deprecation. As mentioned earlier, this needs to be investigated more and tested in practice.

The choice between first or the second technique depends on the available data. There is more data from Wikidata needed for the second technique. The data of the different properties mentioned earlier is for a lot of applications not available. But also for the first technique in lots of cases the data of the software identifier version of application is still missing. It is possible to add the data, but it will be a lot of work. That's why this part of the paper can only be implemented as a proof-of-concept to show if the techniques work or not, but it will take some time before it can be used in a production situation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper brings forward the newly gained insight that monitoring is a better strategy than the predicting. It also aligns better with the Digital Preservation practices of Preservation Watch and Preservation Planning. The methods used in our previous research are still relevant, but they are used in different way.

Not the whole plot is used, but the peaks and inflection points are more important. These points are part of a monitoring system, when they are reached notifications can be send. It is a process you can repeat regularly to create a Watch function.

The second important novelty in this paper is the possibility to compare different plots. This is an important tool to be used in lots of use cases. An important use case is identifying file format succession. This is to monitor if this pattern exists between know file formats with succession. It is not the intention to identify all file formats that have a succession with another file format in a repository, otherwise you could have two different file formats that have a similar successive plots. It is important to keep in mind that the expert decides what is relevant to compare. The technique can't be used to find random patterns, because the possibility is that these patterns do exist, but have no meaning. [23].

It is also possible to use it to compare the outcome of an organization against a global aggregated data set of multiple repositories. This is important to evaluate the local situation and to identify anomalies in the outcomes. These anomalies can be due to the local context and can lead to wrong conclusions on the obsolescence of a file format in the local context. That's why it is important as a validation tool.

The biggest step forward is with the link between applications and file formats. By using Wikidata an activity score can be calculated and together with the release date a plot can be created. The biggest problem for this to work in a production situation is that there is not enough data available on Wikidata yet. It can be implemented as a proof of concept, but further work on Wikidata is needed to support this use case.

This paper builds upon our earlier work and extents if further. The choice for using the same technique is a conscious one, because it is a simple technique. Hopefully, this will simplify

implementation, allowing more institutions to utilize it for gaining insights into their collections

Another reason to use simple techniques is, because the data quality is low and fewer compute resources are needed. This means it is easier to implement and is useful for more institutions.

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